

Consciousness of Artists Vs Intelligence of Artists: Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Artists' Intelligence.

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ABSTRACT

In the era of Deep Learning, it is no secret that generative artificial intelligence has revolutionized the creative industries by producing marvels of art with a few taps on a touchscreen. This raises the question of the impact of artificial intelligence on an individual's creative expression. An artist's artwork has always been a reflection of her/his conscious observation of sociocultural circumstances, where the artist's intelligence helps to execute that conscious observation. The culture of a society affects artists, and art affects culture. Whatever kind of creative work humankind has been cherishing in the form of paintings, dance, poetry, music, drama, sculpture, calligraphy, and graphics is the result of the consciousness of an artist or a group of artists. Reviewing the literature on the conscious creative practices of artists, the paper aims to explore the impact of Artificial Intelligence on the future of creativity and human culture (Harari, 2021). The comparative analysis of human-created art vs. AI-generated art reveals that AI can quickly generate larger quantities of art that reflect the epitome of intelligence. The paper discusses that the looping patterns of AI-generated art will surely keep offering a stream of unprecedented creativity, but they have the potential to develop a non-human culture that will greatly affect the essence of human consciousness; consequently, transforming human intelligence. If intelligence, natural or synthetic, precedes consciousness, it can gradually extirpate the sensitivity of an artist's emotions. The results of comparative analysis highlight the need to make consciousness a primary goal of human cultural development rather than intelligence; in an attempt to keep human primacy over machines. In light of the analytical discussion, the paper propounds two potential grounds: first, how a non-

human culture will reshape the paradigms of art practices, and second, if AI will also become conscious, then how will it be aligned with the artists' consciousness?

Keywords: deep learning, calligraphy, synthetic culture, recursive self-improvement

Introduction

The precise explanation of “consciousness” has always been a topic of debate among scientists and philosophers. At the most basic level, there has been a consensus that “consciousness” is awareness of one’s internal state as well as external state; the capacity to feel. Intelligence, on the other hand, is interpreted as the cognitive ability: to solve problems; apply knowledge and skills. The renowned neuropsychologist Roger Wolcott Sperry’s research on “Split Brain” has given humankind a simple framework for the otherwise much more complex human brain (Sperry, 1968). The publications on Split Brain indicate that the human left hemisphere is associated with analytical thinking and logic, and the human right hemisphere is associated with intuition and creativity. Since 1960, the popular theory has ignited debate on the interplay of human problem-solving abilities vs. subjective experiences in shaping an individual's behavioral process. Although there have been several studies to reinterpret (Corballis, 2014) or even refute (Jared A. Nielsen, 2013) the left-brain vs. right-brain theory, but the initial idea of the Split-Brain theory still appeals to many. By projecting the IQ vs. Emotion analogy on artists and art practices, the study aims to compare man-made art with machine-made art to synthesize the impact of artificial intelligence on artist intelligence. The paper discusses human creative behavior and its effects on the creation of culture. From the earliest traits of human creative expressionism, the decorative Chauvet Cave, to 21st-century holograms, humankind has been creating, witnessing, and cherishing multiple genres of art and design. There has been a gap in understanding what kind of cultural stage the AI-produced art will set for the creative instincts of Generation Alpha and Generation Beta. The paper emphasizes on the supremacy of human consciousness while predicating why intelligence must not precede consciousness.

Methodology

The study employs a desk research approach, in which websites and online articles serve as the primary sources for information collection. The assessment of the collected information has been conducted using Qualitative Comparative Analysis. A total of twenty creative genres have been selected to set the ground of study. First, ten examples from varying genres of

creativity have been selected to be demonstrated as proofs of human consciousness, intelligence, and contemplation. Second, ten similar examples have been selected from the same genres of creativity to be demonstrated as proof of the intelligence of the machine; those creative works were the result of the contemplation of humans, but the intelligence of the machine. The artworks and art genres have been selected on the basis of the fame/recognition they held among art enthusiasts. The research’s theoretical framework incorporates creativity theory (Florence Gabriel, 2023) and posthumanism theory (Centre, The Ethics, 2018) to illustrate the comparative analysis. The research points out the differences of intentionality between the two kinds of art: man-made art vs. AI-made art and its possible effect on the future of human conscious

creative practices.

Literature Review

Beginning the literature from human creativity and reviewing the earliest traits of human creative expressionism, such as cave art. Going 36,000 years back to review the approximately 1,000 pictorial drawings at Grotte Chauvet-Pont d'Arc (RA, n.d.). The humans used charcoal, hematite, and finger tracings on limestone to create remarkable visuals of animals, signs, marks, dots, the lower body of females, motifs, and stencils. A few examples of cave art showed engravings with sharp tools. It reemphasizes the question of what intuition persuades a human to create art.

Figure 1

Grotte Chauvet-Pont d'Arc

Note. The Decorated Cave of Pont d'Arc, located in Ardèche, Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, Southern France (SRA DRAC RA). The cave is mentioned in the list of the UNESCO World Heritage sites.

The use of sharp tools in many cave arts by prehistoric humans shows the significance of early humans' ability to think and solve problems, while tools have been seen by many archaeologists as a means of protection and survival for early humans. Furthermore, the use of charcoal at Grotte Chauvet-Pont d'Arc shows it was prepared to be used for creative purposes. Not as a means of survival (Clottes, 2023). The earliest traits of human creativity gave a

window to peep into human nature, human minds, and the process behind the creation of the earliest art (Gross, February 3, 2020). From hunger to hunting, from needs to wishes, from emptiness to fulfillment, humans respond to every scenario with either logical reasoning or with free-spirited creative expression. The study connects a series of questions with potential answers as follows: When do humans create art? Humans create art when they find inspiration for the art (Popova). How do they get art inspiration? They get inspiration through their conscious observation. What do they observe? They observe what's around them. What's around them? Life is happening around them; mundane life, tough life, easy life, sociocultural norms associated with life. What attribute gives a human the title of artist? Is it safer to say the phenomenon of contemplation makes a human an artist? Artists contemplate. Now, there are so many humans. They all contemplate in their unique way, as well as in similar ways to

each other by imitating each other's behaviors. Collective Human behaviors form a culture, making humans cultural entities. Cultural Transmissions deeply influence creative practices. The only common factor among all the great art pieces is human consciousness to contemplate deeply and express that contemplated conclusion with intelligence. All genres of art have been a result of human contemplation. The humans had a fear of mortality, and they created the Great Pyramid of Khufu (Waldek, 2024).

Figure 2

The Great Sphinx and Khufu's Pyramid

Note. Located at the Giza Plateau, Egypt. The pyramid was built as a tomb to shelter the Pharaoh's body and aid his journey to the afterlife. Photo: Getty Images. (Waldek, 2024).

A human yearned to discover calm in nature; he painted Water Lilies.

Figure 3

Water Lilies

Note. Painting by the artist Claude Monet (1906), oil on canvas (The Art Institute of Chicago).

A human wanted to eternalize his association with another human being, and he commanded the creation of the Taj Mahal.

Figure 4
Taj Mahal

Note. Taj Mahal, a mausoleum located in the Agra District in *Uttar Pradesh*, India. Its construction started in 1632 AD and completed in 1648 AD (Encyclopædia Britannica, 2026).

A photojournalist, during his noble pursuit of exploring the impact of war, such as refugees and the living conditions of displaced communities, caught the eye of an Afghan refugee girl. The photojournalist captured the portrait of the green-eyed girl. The striking stare of that girl later became a symbol of resilience and featured on the front cover of *National Geographic Magazine*.

Figure 5

Afghan Girl

Note. Afghan Girl (Sharbat Gula) photographed by the National Geographic photojournalist Steve McCurry, at Pakistan, in 1984 (Schulze, 2019).

A human who desired to express the delicacy of human feelings, she sang the finest of melodies.

Figure 6

Madam Noor Jahan, The Singer

Note. Pakistani playback singer and ghazal vocalist, Madam Noor Jahan (Hidayat, 2024).

A human experienced a moment of fear and anxiety, and he reflected that experience of feeling panic in an artwork: *The Scream*.

Figure 7

The Scream

Note. *The Scream*, pastel and tempera on cardboard, by Edvard Munch, 1893; in the National Museum, Oslo (Zaczek, n.d.). Image: Encyclopedia Britannica.

A human was intelligent and sensitively conscious towards the complex layers of human emotions; he poured his heart out in sonnets (Mark, 2025).

Figure 8

Sonnet 144 by William Shakespeare

Sonnet 144

“

Two loves I have, of comfort and despair,
Which like two spirits do suggest me still:
The better angel is a man right fair,
The worser spirit a woman coloured ill.
To win me soon to hell, my female evil
Tempteth my better angel from my side,
And would corrupt my saint to be a devil,
Wooing his purity with her foul pride.
And whether that my angel be turned fiend
Suspect I may, yet not directly tell;
But being both from me, both to each friend,
I guess one angel in another's hell:
Yet this shall I ne'er know, but live in doubt
Till my bad angel fire my good one out.

Note. Sonnet 144 by William Shakespeare on the theme of psychological conflict, a human's struggle between good and bad

A human moved his boy in such a gymnastical sequence that he left the other humans in awe.

Figure 9

Michael Jackson

Note. The famous American Singer and Dancer, Michael Jackson, who perfectly performed the dance move Moonwalk and revolutionized the music/dance industry of the 1980s (The Pulitzer Prizes, n.d.).

A human's conscious observation of inequality and hypocrisy across various human communities led him to raise his concerns through thought-provoking street art.

Figure 10

Basquiat being "stopped-and-frisked" outside the Barbican Centre (2017)

Note. Mural Art by the artist Banksy, Artwork created in London, Photographed by Ungry Young Man, Image by Flickr.com, Licensed under CC BY 2.0 (Man, 2017).

The only common factor among all the great art pieces is human consciousness to contemplate deeply. The art that stirs the soul is the art that has been created with soul. The study proceeds towards AI-generated art by gathering samples of varying genres to be analyzed in contrast with human-created art.

Figure 11

Note. AI-generated Archaeological Cave Painting (Freepik, n.d.).

Figure 12

AI-generated image, illustrating the construction details of the Pyramid of Giza (Easy-Peasy.AI, 2024)

Note. The image has been created by Easy-Peasy.AI, which is a platform to provide helpful tools for generating creative work (Easy-Peasy.AI, 2024).

Figure 13

Note. AI-generated Water Lilies (Freepik, n.d.).

Figure 14

The Edge

Note. The Edge, a building located in Amsterdam, has been recognized as the smartest building in the world. The picture by Ronald Tilleman (Story by PLP Architecture, n.d.).

Figure 15

The Electrician

Note. The AI-generated image by the renowned artist and photographer Boris Eldagsen. The image was submitted to the Sony World Photography Awards. The image is famous for initiating a thought-provoking global debate among artists and photographers on the concepts of AI and authorship. The Photographer refused to accept the prize, though this image won the contest

and sparked a healthy debate.

The Artificial Intelligence Virtual Artist (AIVA) has become the first AI to secure the title of Composer from SACEM, the society of Authors, Composers and Publishers of Music. SACEM recognizes the contribution of AI by granting AIVA users the legal right to claim their AIVA-generated compositions under specific licensing and copyright terms.

Figure 16

AI in Music (CASTILLO, 2025)

Figure 17

The Scream

Note. The AI-generated recreation (NightCafe Creator, n.d.) of Edvard Munch's famous painting, *The Scream*.

Figure 18

Sonnet generated by ChatGPT

ChatGPT

Share

Yes, ChatGPT can absolutely write a sonnet. Here's an original Shakespearean-style sonnet on the theme of Good vs. Evil, inspired by the poetic tradition of William Shakespeare:

🔥 Sonnet: *The War Within*

Within my soul two rival forces strive,
One robed in light, one draped in shadowed guise;
By one, my nobler virtues stay alive,
By one, dark whispers cloud my clearer eyes.

The gentle voice bids truth and mercy lead,
And plants in me the seeds of righteous deed;
The other tempts with pride and reckless greed,
And fans the flames of every selfish need.

O endless war that rages in my breast,
No peace is found where both lay equal claim;
For one must fall to grant the other rest,
And yield the heart to honor or to shame.

Yet hope persists that light shall still prevail,
Though night may rise, its shadows ever fail.

+ Ask anything

Note. Example of an AI-generated sonnet: to analyze a human-written sonnet with a ChatGPT-generated sonnet.

Figure 19

Dance Motions generated by AI Choreographer (Jin, 2024)

Note. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/387011704_AI-Based_Music_to_Dance_Synthesis_and_Rendering (Jin, 2024).

Figure 20

AI-powered context transfer enabling a complex composition on the second skin (Shih,

2024)

(a)

(b)

Note. (a) original image; (b) generated image (Shih, 2024). Context Transfer of an actual Graffiti, generated by Stable Diffusion. The image has been extracted from the article, authored by Naai-Jung Shih, as part of the Special Issue on Artificial Intelligence, published in MDPI's Societies

The only common factor among all the man-made great art pieces is human consciousness to contemplate deeply and express that contemplated conclusion with intelligence (Hassan, 2024). On the other hand, Generative AI offers powerful tools, models, chatbots, programs, and platforms for generating high-quality art. The AI-powered tools have revolutionized the process that humans call “creation” (Glover, 2025).

Discussions and Results

The comparison between art created by Humans and art generated by AI-powered platforms; by reviewing the literature on both, the study postulates that Human-created art reflects the essence of the soul and machine-created art reflects the peak of intelligence. Humans have their hands as the tool to create art, and machines have algorithms. Knowing the fact that algorithms have also been initially designed by humans, interpreting the stage where humans have AI as a tool/platform for creating art, such as: Visual Artists and Creative Designers have MidJourney, DALL-E, and Stable Diffusion for creating well-composed visuals. Authors have ChatGPT and Clause.ai for creative writing. Melodists have AIVA for innovative compositions of melodies, etc. After looking at the literature of AI-generated art, one finds pretty amazing pieces of art. For example, one can find amazing digital paintings, conceptual art, moving graphics, smart buildings, and well-composed portraits; one can even recognize the relatable emotions and solutions in the AI-generated art. But the question is “the soul”, the consciousness; the very essence of human emotions, and the process of slow but conscious contemplation. Is it there? And if one’s answer is yes, it is there because AI primarily generates what Humans programmed algorithms to generate. Alright, AI is generating. The generative AI is generating and generating and will keep generating, generating, generating, and humans will keep consuming.

Table 1

Name of Generative AI	How the AI-powered tool/model is useful for the Imaginative Practices of Creators, Artists, and Aesthetes.
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Tools/Models.	
ChatGPT	A useful tool for creative writers to compose text-based content quickly and with versatility. It aids creators in the process of brainstorming as well.
AIVA	A tool for Melodists to generate original symphonic works.
DALL-E	A tool for Visual Artists to create conceptual art.
Stable Diffusion	An AI model for artists and designers to create graphics, illustrations, and image remixes
MidJourney	A tool for Graphic Designers and Digital Artists to create photorealistic visuals and cinematic images.
DeepDream	A technique that assists artists in creating psychedelic images and surreal visuals.
Spacemaker - AI	A tool for Architecture Designers to plan sites (real estate development) and design layouts for buildings (housing projects) while enabling multiple experimentation with design layouts.
AI-singing (aisinging.ai)	A platform for Music Artists to generate melodic voices and vocal tracks.
Hypar	A platform for Architects and Constructors to automate architectural tasks, 3D modeling, and logical space solutions while swiftly producing multiple variations and building's feasibility models.
TestFit	A tool for architects and urban planners to explore Land Development Planning, such as residential land planning, commercial land planning, and industrial land planning. It evaluates the site's feasibility while offering 3D Visualization.
Move.ai	A platform for VFX Artists, Animators, Film Makers, and Choreographers to create motion data to be used in virtual productions, such as in Game Animations.
Runway ML	A comprehensive toolkit for Digital Media Artists to generate and edit images, videos, sounds, animations, and text, and to produce original cross-media content. What makes Runway ML unique is that it integrates multiple AI models.
Claude.ai	A web platform for researchers, developers, and analysts to solve, code, and draft insightful content. It works like a conversational assistant that safely assists in long-form reasoning.

It looks amazing when man and machine work on a strategically measured, aligned wavelength, where man commands and machine executes. The above-mentioned (Table 1) is an exciting example of that.

The paper further examines the AI's feature of "Recursive Self-Improvement." (Sviokla, 2026). This feature of AI allows AI-powered models to keep improving their problem-solving capacity and keep generating better and better in a recursive cycle. The intelligence and continuity of this feature indicate the possibility that AI models would not need any programming, instruction, or feed from humans; they will keep producing better creativity while humans will keep consuming. It will

eventually create a type of art that will transmit a non-human culture. For pictorial illustration:

Diagram 1

To understand the pattern of recursive self-improvement: from playful creative intelligence (in yellow dots) to explosion of intelligence (in red dots), to surpass intelligence of humans

Recursive Self-Improvement.....

.....

.....

The technological advancements have always been unprecedented to many and have always offered smarter solutions, but when it comes to Artificial General Intelligence, it directly challenges human agency on strategic thinking with deep contemplation. For instance, the paper cites a study by Edouard Machery, a philosopher and Professor at the University of Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, and Brian Porter, a renowned academic researcher. Their study reveals that AI-generated poetry is indiscernible from human-created poetry (Edouard Machery, 2024). The majority of the participants from their focal group granted higher ranks to AI-generated poems than human-written poems by the glorious English Poets. Just imagine a human could be

William

Shakespeare, Rumi, Dante, Li Bai, Hafez, Parveen Shakir, Dickens, Sylvia Plath, and a young student of literature would prefer to ignore those humans and take solace in AI-generated literature. Or it can be postulated that coming generations can prefer soulless work over a soulful work, and it is not just about who validates an artist's work or who does not; it is more about what kind of culture it will be producing for human sentimental growth. Now, for empathetic understanding, take an example from one's childhood. A human grew up seeing his/her father or grandfather, or any Aunt or uncle, spending their leisure time listening to a particular song on their radio or gramophone written by a famous poet. That particular child human unconsciously developed a cognition for that poet or the poet's philosophy in his/her head. A child may never express his likeness or dislikeness of that poet, but it stays in his unconsciousness; in his head, and the poet's philosophy will transmit to his next generation without that child; now a grown-up adult, consciously putting any effort into it. The philosophy of a poet will get transmitted like any other cultural transmission.

Now, seeing it through the study of Edouard Machury, what will be the essence of cultural transmission when poetry or philosophy is the idea of synthetic "intelligence" without having any consciousness or mindfulness? If AI takes over the culture, then it will be a synthetic culture, and it will influence the human practice of contemplation; an artificial contemplation, without having an essence or soul but having intelligence only.

The paper propounds two grounds for further scope:

How will a synthetic culture reshape the paradigms of art practices?

Second, if AI will also become conscious, then how will it be aligned with the artists' consciousness?

By putting consciousness and intelligence in alignment across each other while projecting the 1960s theory of Left brain vs. Right Brain, the study assesses the influence of AI in creative practices of the 21st century.

For example, referring to a few popular AI visual generators between the years 2023 and 2024 was (Remsik, 2023): MidJourney (Remsik, 2023): DALL-E (Remsik, 2023): Adobe Firefly (Costin, 2024)

Figure 21

Midjourney Discord

Note. The interface: *The channel list, Server List, Chat Feed, and Member list* (Midjourney).

Generation Z is aware of these AI models and tools, but the question lies in whether they are aware of contemporary artists of their age. The “artist”, not the “influencers” or the point, can be rephrased: is Generation Z inspired by craftsmen, or are they influenced by machines and algorithms only? Or it can be restated as: Is Generation Z willing to produce art manually, or do they wish machines to create art for them? If the research conducted on a focal group in the University of Pittsburgh reveals that the participants granted higher ranks to AI-generated poems than to human-written poems by glorious poets (Edouard Machery, 2024) then the creative trajectory of Generation Beta looks inevitably AI-inspired.

It looks possible that the contemplation process of Generation Beta would be deeply under the influence of a synthetic culture, the culture that has deep roots in artificial intelligence. On the one hand, the discussion sections of the paper send an alarming signal about human practices of creative expression in the near future; on the other hand, it reemphasizes the ideas of post-humanism (Press, 2017). By putting the ideas of post-humanism in the light of artificial super intelligence, the human creative brain looks like a naïve entity, not a master creator.

Conclusion

In light of the versatile patterns of AI-generated creative art produced by artists of Millennials, Generation Z, and Generation Alpha, the paper infers that AI-oriented tools will be an integral part of the creative practices of artists from Generation Beta. The AI-powered tools can offer hundreds of well-composed design variations, mesmerizing artworks, and simplified solutions for complex problems.

The Millennials, Generation Z, and Generation Alpha have been executing creative practices with the tools and models of AI with immense proficiency. It is true for a certain stratum of Generation X as well. But Generation Z and Generation Alpha got introduced to the realm of creativity through an abundance of digital screens (Qureshi, 2025), so artists of these generations are prone to reliance on digital devices for

firsthand knowledge more than human-given information. The AI's feature of Recursive Self-Improvement will keep offering Generation Beta the cutting-edge marvels of art and innovation, and consequently, a culture that might be a result of AI-produced creativity, not the human-produced, consciously nurtured idea of a creative culture. Just like the artificiality of Artificial Intelligence, its offered culture, will be a synthetic culture.

The human hemisphere has been the central core of all ingenious developments on the planet Earth, an authentic source that did not require any synthetic brilliance to perform the genuine function of thinking. This supremacy of the human hemisphere has been creating marvels of innovative art by relying on its neural system. Since the arrival of Artificial Intelligence, humans have been sharing their tasks with AI while gradually sharing the task of thinking and problem-solving as well. Now, AI does the task of problem-solving and creativity while human mind accepts ready-to-use ideas offered by AI. This disrupts the cycle of the human thinking process. By not letting the human brain do the function of thinking, the AI can dominate the human brain if being used as the ultimate assistant always. The generation Alpha and Generation Beta's ability to think autonomously can be damaged by pre-determined solutions offered by artificial intelligence.

Although the influence of artificial intelligence can undermine the essence of conscious creative practices, its prudently strategic implementation can assist humankind in controlling the greatest possible capacity of this technological advancement. The critical aspect is to apply human-centric strategies on the usage of AI to prevent this technology from diminishing the artists' unique capacity for creative thinking (Farooq, 2025). Artists must use AI as an assistant, not as an ultimate mentor. The intelligence of machines must not surpass the uniqueness of human-centric conscious creativity, or else the AI hegemony will make digital colonization inevitable while making artists bear the brunt of technological subjugation. Eventually, it is not just about celebrating art but also about calibrating art tools to protect the very bodies of its appreciators, the humans.

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